

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF DEEP LEARNING-BASED MALWARE DETECTION TECHNIQUES FOR ENHANCED NETWORK SECURITY

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Abstract

Network security now faces new and challenging problems as a result of the rise in cyber threats and the creation of malware. Modern security methods are necessary as malicious actors grow more skilled in their techniques. Deep learning-based techniques are better in this aspect since they can learn from vast datasets, spot trends, and achieve a high degree of generalization for unknown forms of malware. This work aims to establish the accuracy of malware detection by proposing and executing a comparative investigation of the different hybrid deep learning frameworks. Metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, scalability, and efficiency used to evaluate these models in relation to how well they recognize known samples and zero-day assaults. To have a thorough and realistic setup, the two malware datasets that are readily available online used for testing as well as training. The study investigates each model's practical applicability in even real-time network security settings, as well as its computing complexity. Therefore, the goal of this research is to further the development of deeper learning-based detection techniques that are more intelligent and adaptable in order to reduce malware threats. In conclusion, the goal of this study is to facilitate the application of theory, allowing for the creation of networks that are more resilient to sophisticated malware attacks in the future. In this research, CNN and ANN models for malware detection. The CNN achieved a high accuracy of 98.44%, while the ANN demonstrated 95.88% accuracy. A comparative analysis of these models was conducted to evaluate their performance, highlighting the strengths and applicability.

Keywords:

Cyber security, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Malware, Network security

1. Introduction

Particularly, the threat of malware has increased dramatically, posing a major risk to individuals, companies, and even whole nations. Malware is no longer identifiable by heuristic or signature scanning on a terminal since it has changed with the digital world. These techniques are useless for identifying recently discovered or modified malware strains, or zero days, because they rely on pattern matching or signatures. However, this has been associated with limitations that have necessitated the use of alternative techniques, such as deep learning, a subset of machine learning, to improve it Fei et al.(2020). It should be noted that deep learning models are ideal for identifying hidden malware since, unlike the majority of traditional techniques, they are able to learn characteristics from a raw data set. When applied to large amounts of data, deep learning models are an effective tool for detecting complex patterns and regular or irregular traffic in executable files or communications. They also offer a realistic testbed environment for resolving the shortcomings of the current dataset, which include accurate labeling, recent and complex attack diversity, and the inability to capture complete network information. Lastly, compare the BoT-IoT dataset to the benchmark datasets and assess its dependability for forensic purposes using various statistical and machine learning techniques. The foundation for enabling botnet detection across particular networks is provided by this study Koroniotis et al.(2019).

Because hackers to breach networks, malware assaults pose a serious threat to network security today. Sometimes it might be challenging for traditional malware detection methods, including heuristics and signature algorithms, to keep up with the threat's rapid spread. Deep learning is one kind of artificial intelligence that is becoming more and more popular Vinayakumar et al.(2019). It establishes new criteria for identifying unlawful activity by observing intricate data patterns that are usually difficult to identify. Convolutional neural networks, or CNNs, are one type of deep learning based malware detection technique that has garnered a lot of interest lately. Neural networks (RNN) and deep belief networks (DBN). Manage unforeseen volumes of data and identify anomalies that traditional methods could miss. This study's objective is to It aims to ascertain which model provides the highest detection rates and speed and can perform effectively in real-world scenarios Venkatraman et al.(2019). According to our experiments, the micro-security add-on that uses the recommended CNN model can identify phishing attempts with a 93.58% F-1 score and 94.3% accuracy. The back-end LSTM model uses all harmful data points in the dataset to detect Botnet assaults with 94.80% accuracy. Therefore, the results show that the suggested method may identify assaults in a distributed manner at the device and back-end levels De La Torre Parra et al.(2020)

The investigation's findings will be helpful in creating network protection plans against different types of malware. The methodologies employed in the creation and growth of malware, together with the diversity and complexity of attack structures, have made traditional methods of malware detection far less effective Alkahtani and Aldhyani (2021). Enough analysis done on these techniques to determine how effective they are in detecting malware within the context of network security. The problem is in determining which of these options to use in order Tian et al. (2020).

It is any program that is purposefully made to harm a computer, server, or network Malware encompasses a wide variety of dangerous programs, each with its own attack method and effects, including viruses, worms, Trojan horses, ransomware, and spyware. Security systems have historically

depended on signature-based detection, which identifies known malware by comparing it to a database of malware signatures that have been previously seen. To determine the probability that a file or process is malicious, these models may be trained on either static (like bytecode or file structure) or dynamic (like behavior patterns during execution) data Aslan and Samet (2020).

2. Related Work

Aslan and Samet (2020) presented malicious software, or malware, is growing at an alarming rate, according to recent research. Some malware may conceal itself in a system by employing various obfuscation tactics. The malware must be identified before it has a chance to impact many systems in order to safeguard computer systems and the Internet. Numerous researches on methods for detecting malware have been conducted recently. Malware identification, however, is still a challenge. Both heuristic-based and When it comes to recognizing known malware, signature based detection algorithms are fast and successful but signature-based detection in particular has not been able to identify novel malware. However, for unknown and complex malware, behavior-based, model-checking, and cloud-based methods work effectively; and methods based on mobile devices, deep learning, and other techniques also surface to identify some known and new malware. But no method is able to identify every piece of malware in the wild.

Alzaylaee et al. (2020) acknowledged since 2012, the has dominated the market for due to its popularity, Android malware has increased significantly in recent years. Thanks to significant developments in Android malware obfuscation and detection avoidance tactics, many traditional malware detection methods are now ineffective. With the use of systematic input generation and real-time analysis, DL Droid, a deep learning system, can identify dangerous Android applications. Here we discuss testing done on actual devices using over 30,000 programs, some of which are excellent and some of which are awful. Further, experiments were carried out to evaluate the stateless technique's code coverage and detection performance in comparison to the deep learning method system with the elegant input generating strategy. While it is true that DL-Droid with state-based input creation outperforms the state-of-the-art approaches, the findings do highlight the need of better input production for dynamic analysis.

Bhatia (2020) presented is a major worry these days because each domain transmits a significant quantity of data every hour. In order to protect data, this study offers a detailed assessment on the use of neural networks for intrusion detection and prevention. This study has examined and contrasted many kinds additionally, utilizing artificial neural networks; a comparative analysis of various methods such as and application based intrusion detection strategies is conducted. The study demonstrates how may be utilized to identify intruders using the intrusion detection system (IDS) approach, protecting the system from any harmful faults that may arise.

Bederna and Szadeczky (2020) addressed There has been a history of illegally infected device groups on the Internet for twenty years. This history demonstrates the development of infection methods, the range of target devices, and their use. The use of advanced data leaking tactics by state-sponsored hacking organizations is thus the current trend. Our paper examines this development with an emphasis on the use of botnets for cyberespionage. In the framework of network science research, lifespan, applied network protocols, and capabilities, we introduce the Botnet architecture. We next examine two instances that illustrate the practical cyber espionage capabilities of this technique: the VPN Filter Botnet and the APT28 group operations.

3. Methodology

The methodology used in this study has been designed to meet each research objective in turn, starting

with data collection and progressing through model training, evaluation, and analysis. In the Google Collab environment, publicly accessible datasets will be trained, validated, and tested using the Python programming language Aslan (2021). This will need utilizing both comparative analysis and experimental procedures to examine the efficacy of the different deep learning approaches to malware detection. This study will make use of the Malicia and Ember research databases, which include publicly available malware data. Before feeding this data into the deep learning models, a number of preprocessing processes need to be finished Zheng et al. (2020). The steps outlined above will help get the data ready for proper processing by machine learning algorithms. Two of the main tactics used at this level are feature extraction and data standardization. In order for deep learning models to recognize patterns in the binary's structure, the malware binaries will be transformed into grayscale images. On the other hand, data about network traffic is arranged based on successive inputs. It makes it easier for deep learning models to comprehend temporal relationships Xiao et al.(2018).

Figure 1. 1 ANN and CNN

(i) Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are perfect for malware detection because they are very good at finding patterns in high-dimensional data. CNNs are more effective than conventional techniques because they can record correlations and spatial dependencies between several features. CNNs are well-known for their reliability in image recognition, and because of their capacity to identify intricate behavioral patterns, their use in malware detection is growing in popularity Hemalatha et al. (2021).

(ii) Artificial Neural Networks

Malware is classified using extracted characteristics and Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs). ANNs use several layers of linked neurons to translate inputs into outputs. When trained on balanced data, they generalize well and perform well on mid-sized datasets Kilincer et al.(2021).

Dataset

100,000 observations and 35 attributes, this dataset offers a comprehensive record of performance and behavioral metrics for both benign and malicious activities. The hash column identifies a distinct process for each observation. The categorization column, which serves as the goal variable for analysis and machine learning models, determines whether a process is malicious or not. The remaining elements help distinguish between malicious and benign activity by capturing technical characteristics of system and process behavior. Features like usage counter (resource use), state (process status), and millisecond (time tracking) aid in the analysis of system activity and scheduling behavior. Process scheduling and priority patterns are reflected by attributes such as prio, static_prio, and policy. Task size, cached_hole_size, and free_area_cache are examples of memory use metrics that monitor memory-intensive tasks, whereas virtual memory operations like vm_pgoff and vm_truncate_count draw attention to odd memory activity that may be a sign of malware.

Figure 1.2 Methodology

4. Results and discussions

The implementation and dataset utilized for the comparative analysis of deep learning-based malware detection methods are the main topics of this chapter. The dataset, which includes 35 characteristics and 100,000 observations, records important system-level parameters including CPU cycles, memory consumption, and process activity. These characteristics make it possible to spot patterns that set malware apart from safe operations. Preprocessing the data, using feature selection strategies, and leveraging deep learning models like CNNs and ANNs are all part of the implementation process. The models are assessed and compared using a variety of performance indicators, such as accuracy and F1-score, which offer insights into the best methods for boosting network security Vijayalakshmi and Karthika (2021).

Table 1. 1 CNN Model Accuracy and Loss

Model	Accuracy	Loss
CNN	98.44%	0.1504

Table 1. 2 Classification Reports CNN

DL Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
CNN	0.98	1.00	0.95	0.98

Table 1. 3 ANN Model Accuracy and Loss

Model	Accuracy	Loss
ANN	95.88%	0.1962

Table 1. 4 Classification Reports ANN

DL Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
ANN	0.95	1.00	0.95	0.98

CNN and ANN Model Comparison Plot

In the context of malware detection, the bar chart contrasts the accuracy and loss of two models: Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and Artificial Neural Network (ANN). With an accuracy of 98.44% as opposed to 95.88% for the ANN model, the CNN model outperforms it in accurately classifying malware. Furthermore, compared to the ANN model, which has a somewhat larger loss value of 0.1962, the CNN model has a lower loss value of 0.1504 indicating great optimization and reduced error rates during training Akhtar (2022). These findings highlight how CNN performs better than ANN in terms of accuracy and loss, giving it a better option for malware detection jobs.

Figure 1. 3 CNN And ANN Model Comparison

Comparative Analysis

The table highlights significant gains in accuracy, precision, recall, and F-measure by comparing performance measures between earlier research and our suggested deep learning-based malware detection approaches. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Gated Recurrent Units (GRUs) are two deep learning models that were used in the earlier research Vaddadi et al. (2022). With a batch size of 65 and training across 100 epochs, the CNN model obtained 90.58% accuracy. The performance was

balanced but somewhat effective, as evidenced by the accuracy of 0.92, recall of 0.91, and F-measure of 0.91. In a similar vein, the GRU model with the same training settings showed a slightly lower accuracy of 88.29%, along with precision, recall, and F-measure of 0.90 and 0.88, respectively. Even while these findings show a respectable degree of efficacy, they also point out certain shortcomings in identifying the complex patterns of malware behavior, calling for more developments in model design and training optimization. In order to fill these gaps, our study suggests improved models that produce noticeably better outcomes Analysis et al. (2022). With an astounding accuracy of 98.44%, a flawless precision score of 1.00, a recall of 0.95, and an F-measure of 0.98, the CNN in our research is particularly noteworthy. This was accomplished notably with a batch size of 64 and a training configuration of 50 epochs, highlighting the effectiveness of our method in obtaining excellent performance with lower computing resources. The resilience of our model's feature extraction and classification capabilities is demonstrated by the decrease in training epochs without sacrificing accuracy Tayyab et al. (2022). Furthermore, our research presents an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model, which similarly produced outstanding outcomes Ali et al. (2022). With a higher batch size of 512 and training during just 10 epochs, the ANN attained an accuracy of 95.88%, a precision of 1.00, a recall of 0.95, and an F-measure of 0.98. This result is especially remarkable considering the ANN's ease of use and low training requirements, underscoring its potential for quick and effective malware detection in situations when time or computing resources are crucial.

Table 1. 5 Comparative Analysis

	Algorithms	Epoch	Batch Size	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F Measure
Previous work	CNN	100	65	90.58%	0.92	0.91	0.91
	GRU	100	65	88.29%	0.90	0.90	0.88
Our Work	CNN	50	64	98.44%	1.00	0.95	0.98
	ANN	10	512	95.88%	1.00	0.95	0.98

Figure 1. 4 Comparative Analysis**Figure 1. 5** Line Chart

5. Conclusion

Malware detection tackles the growing danger of malware in the digital age and the requirement for cutting-edge defenses against these threats. Against complex malware variants like polymorphic and zero-day threats, traditional malware detection approaches like signature-based and heuristic methods have become progressively less successful. Because these techniques rely on preset patterns or behaviors, they are reactive and cannot keep up with the rapid evolution of cyber threats. The study also draws attention to the shortcomings of conventional approaches. Although heuristic approaches are more flexible, they frequently produce large false-positive rates, whereas signature-based techniques struggle against novel malware varieties since they rely on existing patterns. The paper highlights that in order to improve detection capabilities in actual network settings, these drawbacks call for the use of sophisticated DL models. In order to assess the performance of different DL models, the Mushtaq et al. (2022). These datasets were selected due to their capacity to accurately label, capture recent attack trends, and reflect a variety of malware behaviors. As a result, deep learning (DL)-based methods have become effective instruments that provide enhanced malware detection scalability, accuracy, and flexibility. Future developments can open the door to more secure digital ecosystems by expanding on these discoveries Chaganti et al. (2022).

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